

Synthesis of some Hydroxy Cyclohexyl Carbinol Phosphates and Related Compounds*

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In order to study which atoms or functional groups of glucose-6-phosphate are responsible for binding to the enzyme glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, a series of hydroxylated cyclohexane carbinol phosphates and related compounds which resembled glucose-6-phosphate sterically, were synthesised. The aromatic carboxylic acids or esters containing hydroxy groups in appropriate position were reduced by catalytic hydrogenation into the *cis*- and *trans*-cyclohexane derivatives which were then converted to the corresponding hydroxy cyclohexane carbinols by reduction with lithium aluminium hydride. The carbinols were phosphorylated to give the diphenyl-phosphoryl esters which on hydrogenolysis gave the desired phosphates (IV-IX). Synthesis of 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydrofuran, 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran, and 2-hydroxy-6-hydroxymethyl-tetrahydropyran phosphates (X, XI, XVI) have also been accomplished. Evaluation of these compounds, however, revealed that they were weakly inhibitory or non-inhibitory to the enzyme glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase.

The conversion of glucose-6-phosphate to 6-phosphogluconolactone by glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase is an important enzymatic step in the carbohydrate metabolism but few studies have been made to determine which of the atoms or functional groups of glucose-6-phosphate are important for binding to the enzyme. Consequently, it was of interest to synthesise some compounds which would resemble glucose-6-phosphate sterically and to evaluate their binding capacities with glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase. Such compounds would be of further interest as inhibition of tumour growth by antimetabolites of hexose monophosphate pathway intermediates was observed recently¹. This paper describes the synthesis of a number of hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol phosphates and some related compounds. However, the compounds prepared were weakly inhibitory or non-inhibitory to the enzyme glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase.

The cyclohexane carbinol was chosen as the nucleus which was hydroxylated at different positions and then phosphorylated to give the corresponding carbinol phosphates resembling glucose-6-phosphate sterically. In general, the aromatic carboxylic acids or esters (I) containing hydroxy groups in appropriate position were catalytically hydrogenated and the products separated into *cis*- and *trans*-cyclohexane derivatives which were then converted to the corresponding hydroxy cyclohexyl carbinols by reduction with lithium aluminium hydride (LAH). The hydroxy substituted cyclohexane carboxylic acids were selected as they offered the possibility of separation and proof of structure by chemical means. The carbinols (II) on treatment with diphenylphosphoryl chloride in pyridine gave the diphenylphosphoryl esters (III) which on hydrogenolysis gave the desired

* Presented at the Convention of Chemists at Kharagpur, December, 1969.

1. M. B. Sahasrabudhe, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1967, **26**, 243.

phosphates (Chart I, IV-IX). The viscous liquid phosphates, if necessary, were characterized as crystalline *bis*-cyclohexylammonium salts.

trans-2-Hydroxycyclohexane carboxylic acid² was prepared by base isomerisation of a mixture of methyl *cis* and *trans*-2-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylate obtained by catalytic hydrogenation of methyl salicylate. The *trans*-acid was then converted by LAH reduction to *trans*-2-hydroxy cyclohexyl carbinol³. *cis*-2-Hydroxy- Δ^3 -cyclohexene-1-carbinol was prepared by LAH reduction of methyl-*cis*-2-acetoxy- Δ^3 -cyclohexene carboxylate², which in turn was obtained by Diels-Alder reaction between methyl acrylate and 1-acetoxy-1,3-butadiene⁴. Preparation of *cis*-3-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylic acid by catalytic hydrogenation of *m*-hydroxy benzoic acid was achieved in poor yield by Clarke and Owen⁵ using Raney nickel at 150° under high pressure and by Noyce and Denney⁶ using platinum dioxide. The *cis*-acid was, however, isolated in 28% yield from a mixture of *cis* and *trans*-acid-obtained by hydrogenation of *m*-hydroxy benzoic acid using a 5% rhodium-on-alumina

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3. E. E. Smissman and R. A. Mode, *ibid.*, 1957, **79**, 3447.
4. W. J. Bailey and R. Barclay, Jr., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 328.
5. M. F. Clarke and L. N. Owen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2108.
6. D. S. Noyce and D. B. Denney, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5912.

catalyst. Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the *cis*-acid gave *cis*-3-hydroxy cyclohexyl carbinol⁶. Hydrogenation of ethyl-*p*-hydroxybenzoate in presence of 5% rhodium on alumina afforded the ethyl-4-hydroxycyclohexanecarboxylate, which was prepared previously by Owen and Robins⁷ using Raney nickel at high temperature and pressure. Instead of separating the isomeric acids at this stage, ethyl-4-hydroxy cyclohexane carboxylate was reduced with LAH and the *cis*- and *trans*-diols⁷ were isolated by distillation.

In addition, 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydrofuran phosphate (X) and 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran phosphate (XI) were prepared by the general method of phosphorylation and hydrogenolysis (Chart II). Synthesis of 2-hydroxy-6-hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran phosphate (XII) proceeded in the same way but in the final stage of hydrogenolysis, the 2-benzyloxy group in 2-benzyloxy-6-hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran diphenyl phosphate (XIV) could not be removed even under different conditions of hydrogenation. However, mild acid hydrolysis of the hydrogenated 2-benzyloxy product gave (XVI) which reduced Benedict's solution. Racemic 2-hydroxymethyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-pyran was prepared by sodium borohydride reduction of acrolein dimer⁸.

EXPERIMENTAL

The infrared spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer model 137 Spectrophotometer. The melting points were taken in open capillary tubes on a Mel-Temp. apparatus and are corrected. The analyses reported in this paper were performed by Galbraith Microanalytical Laboratories, Knoxville, Tenn., U.S.A.

Cyclohexylcarbinol diphenylphosphate : To a solution of cyclohexanemethanol (8.5 g; 75 m moles) in dry pyridine (20 ml), cooled in freezing mixture, was added 20.16 g. (75.5 m moles) of diphenyl phosphoryl chloride with constant stirring. The mixture was kept overnight at room temperature after which it was poured into crushed ice and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The oily product was extracted with ether, and the ether solution was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The liquid obtained after evaporation of ether *in vacuo* was distilled to give 23.0 g. (88.6%) of pure cyclohexylcarbinol diphenylphosphate as colourless liquid, b.p. 183–85°/0.1 mm. ν in cm^{-1} (Film) : 3050, 2925 (CH); 1580, 1480 (phenyl); 1380 (P = O); 1280 (P–O–C, aromatic). (Found : C, 65.93; H, 6.55; P, 8.39. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_4\text{P}$ requires C, 65.88; H, 6.69; P, 8.94%).

Cyclohexylcarbinol phosphate (IV) : A mixture of 2.0 g. (5.7 m moles) of cyclohexyl carbinol diphenyl phosphate and 200 mg. of platinum dioxide catalyst in ethanol (200 ml.) was hydrogenated at an initial pressure of 3.16 kg/cm^2 at room temperature until the theoretical amount of hydrogen had been absorbed. After filtration, the ethanolic solution was evaporated *in vacuo*, and the crude cyclohexylcarbinol phosphate was obtained as a low-melting solid in quantitative yield (1.1 g.). Repeated crystallizations of the product from benzene-hexane mixture and finally from benzene gave the analytical material as colourless flakes, m.p. 114°. ν in cm^{-1} (KBr) : 2950–2350 (broad; P–O–H); 1260 (P = O); 1050 (P–O–C). (Found : C, 43.05; H, 7.63; P, 15.71. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_4\text{P}$ requires C, 43.29; H, 7.78; P, 15.96%).

7. L. N. Owen and P. A. Robins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 326.

8. R. Zelinski, A. Verbiscar and H. J. Eichel, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 184.

trans-2-Hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol: The reduction of *trans*-2-hydroxycyclohexanone carboxylic acid², m.p. 110° (5.2 g; 36.1 m moles) was carried out with lithium aluminium-hydride (3.5 g.) in 200 ml. of dry ether. The product, isolated in the usual manner, as a liquid (4.17 g.) was distilled to give 3.29 g. (69.7%) of pure *trans*-2-hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol, b.p. 75°/0.09 mm. (reported³ b.p., 103.5–104°/0.9 mm). ν in cm^{-1} (film): 3400 (OH); 2980, 2900 (CH). (Found: C, 64.31; H, 11.00. Calc. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$: C, 64.57; H, 10.83%).

trans-2-Hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol phosphate (V): *trans*-2-Hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol (1.3 g; 10 m moles) was phosphorylated with 2.68 g. (10 mmoles) of diphenylphosphoryl chloride in presence of pyridine according to the method described earlier. The product, *trans*-2-hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol diphenyl phosphate was isolated, as usual, as a colourless liquid, 3.2 g. (88%). ν in cm^{-1} (film); 3500 (OH); 3100, 2950, 2900 (CH); 1600, 1465 (phenyl); 1280 (P = O); 1190 (P–O–C, aromatic); 1025 (P–O–C).

A mixture of the above diphenyl phosphate (3.2 g; 8.8 mmole) and 300 mg. of platinum dioxide in 200 ml. of ethanol was hydrogenated as usual. The product, *trans*-2-hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol phosphate was obtained as colourless viscous liquid in quantitative yield (1.8 g.) ν in cm^{-1} (film); 3300 (OH shoulder); 2950–2200 (P–OH; broad); 1150 (P = O); 1050 (P–O–C).

The phosphate was converted into the *bis*-cyclohexylammonium salts by adding an ethanolic solution of the former to cyclohexylamine in ethanol with stirring. The precipitated solid was separated by filtration and the cyclohexylamine salt was obtained by evaporation of the filtrate *in vacuo*. The latter was crystallized several times from a methanol-ethylacetate mixture to give pure *bis*-cyclohexylammonium salt of *trans*-2-hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol phosphate, m.p. 207–210°. ν in cm^{-1} (KBr): 3450 (OH); 2950–2000 (NH_3^+); 1625, 1560 (NH_3^+). (Found: C, 55.65; H, 10.18; N, 6.37; P, 7.20. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{41}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{P}$ requires C, 55.85; H, 10.11; N, 6.85; P, 7.58%).

cis-2-Hydroxy- Δ^3 -cyclohexene-1-carbinol: Methyl *cis*-2-acetoxy- Δ^3 -cyclohexene carboxylate² was prepared in 54% yield from methyl acrylate and 1-acetoxy-1,3-butadiene⁴. A solution of 7.92 g. (40 mmoles) of this ester in dry ether was reacted with lithium aluminium hydride (3.78 g; 100 mmoles) and the reduction product was isolated in the usual way as a colourless viscous liquid, which on distillation gave 1.8 g. of pure *cis*-2-hydroxy- Δ^3 -cyclohexene-1-carbinol, b.p., 70–71°/0.06 mm. ν in cm^{-1} (film); 3350 (OH); 2925, 3020 (CH); 1650 (C = C). (Found: C, 65.34; H, 9.31. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 65.60; H, 9.44%).

cis-2-Hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol phosphate (VI): To a cooled solution of 0.93 g. (7.26 m moles) of *cis*-2-hydroxy- Δ^3 -cyclohexyl carbinol in dry pyridine (10 ml) was added 1.96 g. (7.3 m moles) of diphenylphosphoryl chloride with constant stirring. The mixture was left overnight, and the liquid product, isolated by the usual way, was distilled *in vacuo* to yield 1.88 g. (72.3%) of *cis*-2-hydroxy- Δ^3 -cyclohexyl-carbinol diphenyl phosphate as a colourless viscous liquid.

A mixture of 1.88 g. (5.2 m moles) of the phosphate ester and 300 mg of platinum dioxide catalyst in ethanol (200 ml) was hydrogenated as before. The crude product was isolated as a colourless liquid (1.0 g.) which on keeping in the cold crystallized. Repeated

crystallizations of this product from a mixture of methanol and chloroform, gave the pure *cis*-2-hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol phosphate as colourless needles, m.p. 138–39°. (Found : C, 39.75; H, 7.22; P, 14.64. $C_7H_{15}O_5P$ requires C, 39.99; H, 7.19; P, 14.74%).

cis-3-Hydroxycyclohexane carboxylic acid : A mixture of *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid (27.6 g; 0.2 mole) and 1.5 g. of 5% rhodium-on-alumina catalyst in 200 ml. of ethanol was hydrogenated at an initial pressure of 3.16 kg/cm². After 90% of the theoretical amount of hydrogen had been absorbed in 30 hrs., further absorption stopped when the catalyst was filtered. The hydrogenation was continued for additional 24 hrs. after addition of 1 g. of the fresh catalyst. The ethanol solution was filtered from the catalyst, and the filtrate was evaporated *in vacuo*. The solid residue was crystallized from ethyl acetate to give 8.09 g. (27.8%) of crystalline solid, m.p. 130–31°. Recrystallization from the same solvent gave pure *cis*-3-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylic acid, m.p. 132° (reported⁶ m.p. 130.5–131.5°).

cis-3-Hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol phosphate (VII) : *cis*-3-Hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol was prepared by lithium aluminium hydride reduction of *cis*-3-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylic acid in 49% yield as a colourless liquid, b.p. 133–34°/4 mm (reported⁶ b.p. 132–34°/4 mm). A solution of *cis*-3-hydroxycyclohexyl-carbinol (2.6 g; 20 m moles) in dry pyridine (15 ml) was treated with 5.36 g. (20 m moles) of diphenylphosphoryl chloride at 0°. The product, *cis*-3-hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol diphenyl phosphate was isolated according to the procedure described earlier, as a viscous colourless liquid, 6 g. (82%).

Hydrogenolysis of the above diphenylphosphate (3.12 g; 8.6 m moles) in presence of 300 mg. of platinum dioxide in 200 ml. of ethanol in the usual way gave *cis*-3-hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol phosphate as a colourless syrup in quantitative yield (1.8 g.). ν in cm⁻¹ (film) : 2950–2300 (P–OH); 1150 (P = O); 1050 (P–O–C). The *bis*-cyclohexylammonium salt of the phosphate was prepared by adding an ethanolic solution of the latter to a solution of cyclohexylamine in ethanol with stirring. The white precipitate immediately formed, presumably of impurity, was removed by filtration. The residue obtained by evaporation of the filtrate *in vacuo* was repeatedly crystallized from methanol-ethylacetate mixture, as colourless crystalline needles, m.p. 200–203°. (Found : C, 55.73; H, 10.04; N, 6.63; P, 7.33. $C_{19}H_{41}O_5N_2P$ requires C, 55.85; H, 10.11; N, 6.85; P, 7.58%).

Ethyl-4-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylate : A mixture of ethyl-*p*-hydroxybenzoate (16.6 g., 0.1 mole) and 1.6 g. of 5% rhodium-on-alumina catalyst in 200 ml. of ethanol was hydrogenated at an initial pressure of 3.16 kg/cm². After the theoretical amount of hydrogen had absorbed, the catalyst was removed by filtration and the ethanolic solution was evaporated *in vacuo* to give a colourless liquid (17 g.). Distillation of the product gave ethyl-4-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylate as a colourless liquid (14.4 g; 83.7%), b.p. 138–40°/14 mm. (reported⁷ b.p., 142–45°/15 mm). ν in cm⁻¹ (film) : 3500 (OH); 2990 (CH); 1735 (ester C = O).

cis- and *trans*-4-Hydroxycyclohexyl carbinol : Ethyl-4-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylate (13.0 g; 75.6 m moles) on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride in the usual way gave a colourless liquid, (7.23 g.; 73.4%), b.p. 121–22°/0.5 mm. Repeated crystallizations of the crude product from acetone and ethylacetate afforded colourless crystals of *trans*-4-hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol, 0.3 g, m.p. 103° (reported⁷ m.p. 103°). The mother-liquor gave

an additional 100 mg. of the same product. ν in cm^{-1} (KBr) : 3300 (OH) : 2925, 2950 (CH). The *trans*-glycol gave a dibenzoate, m.p. 80° (reported⁷ m.p., $80\text{--}81^\circ$).

After separating the *trans*-diol, the liquid residue was distilled to give 3.32 g. (46.1%) of *cis*-4-hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol as a viscous liquid b.p. $125\text{--}26^\circ/1.5$ mm (reported⁷ b.p. $135\text{--}47^\circ/3$ mm.). ν in cm^{-1} (film) : 3350 (OH); 2925 (CH). It formed a *bis* tosylate, m.p. 98° (reported⁷ m.p. 98.5°).

An additional amount of *trans*-diol was obtained by reduction of ethyl-4-hydroxycyclohexane carboxylate by Bouveault-Blanc method⁷.

cis-4-Hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol phosphate (VIII) : *cis*-4-Hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol (1.3 g., 10 m moles) in 5 ml. of pyridine was phosphorylated with 2.68 g. (10 m moles) of diphenylphosphoryl chloride and on working up the product in the usual way *cis*-4-hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol diphenylphosphate was obtained as a viscous liquid, 2.87 g. (80%). ν in cm^{-1} (film) : 3500 (CH); 3100, 2950 (CH); 1595 (phenyl); 1290 (P = O); 1195 (P-O-C, aromatic); 1025 (P-O-C).

Hydrogenolysis of *cis*-4-hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol diphenyl phosphate (2.87 g; 7.9 m moles) in presence of platinum dioxide catalyst (300 mg.) according to the method described earlier afforded *cis*-4-hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol phosphate as a colourless syrup in quantitative yield. ν in cm^{-1} (film) : 3300 (OH); 3000-2300 (broad., P-OH); 1025 (P-O-C). A portion of this liquid phosphate was converted to the *bis*-cyclohexylammonium salt as colourless crystals, m.p. 195° . ν in cm^{-1} (KBr) : 3400 (OH); 2950 (CH); 2800-2000, (NH_3^+); 1625, 1560 (NH_3^+); 1025 (P-O-C). (Found : C, 55.60; H, 10.25; N, 7.01; P, 7.86. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{41}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{P}$ requires C, 55.85; H, 10.11; N, 6.85; P, 7.58%).

trans-4-Hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol phosphate (IX) : *trans*-4-Hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol diphenylphosphate was prepared as a colourless viscous liquid in 80% yield from the corresponding *trans*-diol by the procedure described earlier. A mixture of 1.02 g. (2.77 m moles) of this diphenyl phosphate and 150 mg. of platinum dioxide catalyst in 200 ml. of ethanol was hydrogenated as before and on working up the product, *trans*-4-hydroxycyclohexylcarbinol phosphate was obtained as a syrup in quantitative yield. ν in cm^{-1} (film) : 2950 (CH); 2800-2200 (broad; P-O-H); 1030 (P-O-C).

The *bis*-cyclohexylammonium salt of the above phosphate was prepared and crystallized repeatedly from a mixture of methanol-ethyl acetate as colourless crystalline solid, m.p. $208\text{--}10^\circ$. ν in cm^{-1} (KBr) : 3400 (OH; weak); 2950, 2850 (CH); 2800-2200 (NH_3^+ broad); 1625, 1540 (NH_3^+); 1040 (P-O-C). (Found : C, 55.60; H, 10.08; N, 6.63; P, 7.73. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{41}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{P}$ requires C, 55.85; H, 10.11; N, 6.85; P, 7.58%).

2-Hydroxymethyl tetrahydrofuran phosphate (X) : A solution of 10.2 g. (0.1 mole) of tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol in 20 ml. of dry pyridine was phosphorylated with 26.86 g. (0.1 mole) of diphenylphosphoryl chloride at 0° . The product was isolated by the usual way as a liquid. Distillation of the crude product gave pure 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydrofuran diphenyl phosphate as a colourless liquid, b.p. $165^\circ/0.05$ mm, 28.43 g. (85%). ν in cm^{-1} (film) : 3050, 2980, 2890 (CH); 1590, 1490, 1450 (phenyl); 1295 (P = O); 1190 (P-O-C, aromatic); 1075 (C-O-C); 1025 (P-O-C). (Found : C, 60.91; H, 5.97; P, 15. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_5\text{P}$ requires C, 61.07; H, 5.72; P, 9.27%).

A mixture of 10 g. (30 m moles) of 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydrofuran diphenyl phosphate in 200 ml. of ethanol was hydrogenated in presence of 1 g. of platinum dioxide catalyst and the product was isolated as a colourless syrup in quantitative yield. It was purified by passing a methanolic solution through a Celite pad. The residue after removing the solvent was dried *in vacuo*. ν in cm^{-1} (film); 2900 (CH); 2800–2200 (broad, P–O–H); 1025 (P–O–C). (Found C, 32.77; H, 6.56; P, 17.05. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{P}$ requires C, 32.96; H, 6.63; P, 17.03%).

2-Hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran: A mixture of 13.6 g. (0.12 mole) of acrolein dimer (supplied by Shell Development Co.) and 1.5 g. of platinum dioxide in 200 ml. of ethanol was hydrogenated at an initial pressure of 3.16 kg/cm^2 . After the theoretical amount of hydrogen had absorbed (8 hours), the catalyst was filtered and the filtrate on evaporation *in vacuo* gave a colourless liquid product. Redistillation of this gave the analytically pure 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran as a colourless liquid, b.p. 92.5–3°/26 mm. (reported⁹ b.p., 180–83°/760 mm); yield, 8.4 g. (61.4%). ν in cm^{-1} (film); 3400 (OH); 2925, 2850 (CH); 1090 (C–O–C). (Found: C, 61.85; H, 10.65, Calc. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$: C, 62.04; H, 10.41%). 2-Hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran was prepared by L. Crombie *et al.*⁹ from acrolein dimer by using Raney nickel as catalyst at 60° under 30 atm. pressure.

2-Hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran phosphate (XI): A solution of 2-hydroxy methyl tetrahydropyran (3.64 g; 31.33 m moles) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was phosphorylated with 8.42 g. (31.33 m moles) of diphenyl phosphoryl chloride according to the procedure described earlier. The crude product was distilled to give the pure 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran diphenyl phosphate as colourless liquid, b.p. 168.5°/ mm. Yield 8.27 g. (76.5%). ν in cm^{-1} (film): 3100, 0.06, 2950, 2850 (CH); 1590 (phenyl); 1280 (P = O); 1195 (P–O–C, aromatic); 1075 (C–O–C); 1020 (P–O–C). (Found: C, 62.19; H, 6.08; P, 8.87. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_5\text{P}$ requires C, 62.06; H, 6.07; P, 8.89%).

A mixture of the above diphenylphosphate (4.53 g; 13 m moles) and 400 mg. of platinum dioxide in 200 ml. of ethanol was hydrogenated at an initial pressure of 3.16 kg/cm^2 for 2 hrs. The syrupy product obtained on working up the mixture was decolorized with charcoal (methanol) and the solution was filtered through Celite. The residue obtained after removal of the solvent, was dried *in vacuo* to give the pure 2-hydroxymethyl tetrahydropyran phosphate as a colourless viscous liquid. ν in cm^{-1} (film); 2950 (CH); 2800–2200 (broad, P–OH); 1020 (P–O–C). (Found: C, 36.91; H, 6.87; P, 15.73. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_5\text{P}$ requires C, 36.73; H, 6.67; P, 15.8%).

2-Benzoyloxy-6-hydroxymethyl-tetrahydropyran (XIII): To a stirring solution of 21.6 g. (0.2 mole) of benzyl alcohol containing 100 mg. of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid was added 22.8 g. (0.2 mole) of 2-hydroxymethyl-2,3-dihydro-4H-pyran⁸ over a period of one hr. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for further 2 hrs. The product was taken up in ether (200 ml.) and washed with 1% sodium hydroxide solution and then with water. The ether solution after drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate was evaporated to yield 42.5 g. of a colourless liquid.

An attempt at distillation of a portion of the liquid *in vacuo* resulted partly in decomposition of the product into starting materials and in resinification, possibly due to the

presence of trace of acidic material. The product was then distilled *in vacuo* in presence of 2-3 pellets of sodium hydroxide. 2-Benzoyloxy-6-hydroxymethyl-tetrahydropyran was obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 105-107°/0.07 mm; yield, 29%. ν in cm^{-1} (film): 3400 (OH); 3050, 2950, 2900 (CH); 1600, 1490, 1450 (phenyl); 1030 (C-O-C-O-C). (Found: C, 70.19; H, 7.9. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.28; H, 8.17%).

2-Benzoyloxy-6-hydroxymethyl-tetrahydropyran diphenyl phosphate (XIV): To a solution of (XIII) 3.54 g. (15.9 m moles) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was added slowly with stirring 4.26 g. (15.9 m moles) of diphenylphosphoryl chloride at 0°. After the addition was over, the mixture was kept at room temperature overnight. The product was isolated by the usual procedure to yield the 2-benzoyloxy-6-hydroxymethyl-tetrahydropyran diphenyl phosphate as a colourless syrup. ν in cm^{-1} (film): 3050, 2950 (CH); 1590, 1490, 1450 (phenyl); 1280 (P=O); 1185 (P-O-C, aromatic); 1000-1199 (broad; P-O-C; C-O-C-O-C). An attempt at distillation of a portion of this product *in vacuo* resulted in decomposition.

2-Hydroxy-6-hydroxymethyl-tetrahydropyran phosphate (XVI): A mixture of 2.71 g. (6.2 m moles) of the above compound (XIV) in 200 ml. of ethanol was hydrogenated in presence of 300 mg. of platinum dioxide as usual. The product (XV), obtained as colourless syrup (1.8 g.) showed absence of aromatic bands in the IR but it did not reduce Benedict's solution. ν in cm^{-1} (film): 2950 (CH); 2800-2000 (P-OH, broad), 1000-1100 (P=O, C-O-C-O-C, broad). This syrupy product (1 g.) was stirred with 6N-hydrochloric acid (10 ml) at room temperature when the former gradually dissolved. The mixture was allowed to stand 24 hrs. after which it was evaporated to dryness *in vacuo*. The viscous residue (reduced Benedict's solution) was decolourized with charcoal and then converted to the cyclo-hexylamine salt of 2-hydroxy-6-hydroxymethyl-tetrahydropyranphosphate (XVI) as colourless crystals, m.p. 138-40°. ν in cm^{-1} (KBr): 3450 (OH); 2950 (CH); 2800-2200 (NH_3^+); 1625, 1550 (NH_3^+). (Found: C, 52.46; H, 9.67; N, 6.65; P, 7.58. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{39}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2\text{P}$ requires C, 52.63; H, 9.57; N, 6.82; P, 7.79%).

The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Dr. S. Mitra, Director of this centre for his keen interest and encouragement. This investigation was carried out at the Department of Medicinal Chemistry, State University of New York at Buffalo, N.Y., U.S.A., for which the author is indebted to Professor Howard J. Schaeffer for offering laboratory facilities and valuable suggestions. Thanks are also due to Charles F. Schwender of the same department for the enzymatic measurements.